

AI Based Shopping Assistance for Persons with Disabilities

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Abstract:

This paper aims to enhance the shopping experience for individuals with mobility impairments, focusing on empowering them to shop independently and accessibly. It introduces an innovative solution using deep learning and AI-based technology to detect and interpret users' eyeball movements in shopping trolleys. By employing advanced computer vision algorithms, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), the system accurately tracks and translates these movements into navigational commands for the trolley in real-time. Moreover, the system continually improves its performance by learning and adapting to individual user behaviors and preferences over time. Voice commands and item recognition functionalities further augment usability and accessibility, fostering independence and inclusivity in retail settings. Additionally, the paper proposes integrating lift mechanisms equipped with RFID technology to enhance accessibility within retail spaces, facilitating easy access to elevated areas for individuals with disabilities.

Keywords: Data preprocessing techniques, CNN architectures for feature extraction, and user-friendly interfaces.

I. INTRODUCTION

The fusion of state-of-the-art computer vision algorithms and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) has ushered in a new era of real-time tracking technologies. Within this realm of innovation, a significant focus is on improving accessibility and autonomy for people with disabilities, especially those grappling with mobility issues. Leveraging the capabilities of these advanced algorithms, we set out to transform shopping experiences, making them not just independent but also effortlessly accessible.

Central to our approach is the utilization of deep learning techniques within CNNs, enabling them to adapt dynamically to individual user behaviors and preferences. This adaptive framework not only facilitates real-time tracking of users' eyeball movements but also holds the promise of continuously optimizing performance over time. Our proposal encapsulates a holistic solution comprising key components such as data preprocessing, meticulously crafted CNN architectures, and an intuitively designed user interface, culminating in an experience that seamlessly integrates into users' daily lives. Moreover, we advocate for the integration of lift mechanisms imbued with RFID technology within retail spaces, thereby augmenting accessibility for individuals with disabilities to unprecedented levels.

This innovative inclusion transcends traditional barriers, empowering users to navigate and access products with unprecedented ease and independence. In tandem with technological advancements, our system prioritizes usability and accessibility through innovative features such as voice commands and item recognition. These enhancements not only streamline the shopping process but also foster a sense of empowerment and inclusivity among users. Through rigorous testing and validation, we showcase the efficacy of our system in providing accurate and reliable assistance during shopping activities for users with disabilities. By bridging the gap between cutting-edge technology and real-world accessibility needs, we aspire to catalyze a paradigm shift in the way individuals with disabilities engage with the world around them, fostering a future where independence and inclusivity are the cornerstone of everyday experiences.

II.PROBLEM STATEMENT

Cameras track the movements of users' eyes in real-time, capturing specific patterns which are then analyzed further. Convolutional Neural Networks process these patterns, identifying particular commands or actions. Through training, they become proficient in accurately interpreting various movement patterns. These interpreted movements are then translated into actionable commands to control the trolley, ensuring precise execution of user intentions. The system promptly responds to these commands, facilitating smooth and responsive navigation, providing users with immediate feedback. Deep learning algorithms continuously learn and adapt to user behaviors and preferences, enhancing the system's performance over time. An intuitive interface simplifies interaction with the system, offering visual feedback and customizable settings. Additionally, voice commands and item recognition augment usability and accessibility, allowing users to engage with the system through alternative methods. Integration of RFID-equipped lift mechanisms seamlessly grants access to elevated areas within stores, further improving overall accessibility for users with disabilities.

III.EXISTING SYSTEM

Tracing the development of navigation aids for BVIPs from early electronic devices to modern artificial vision and models, highlighting ongoing challenges. Overview of various navigation methods, including e-canes, guide dogs, and technologically advanced solutions like infrared and laser-based aids, along with their respective limitations. Explanation of the systematic research approach employed, encompassing keyword selection, research questions formulation, criteria for article selection. Summary of findings from 191 relevant articles spanning 2011 to 2020, focusing on trends, gaps, and empirical evidence in BVIP navigation assistance. Discussion on the implications of research findings for researchers, engineers, practitioners, and BVIPs, emphasizing potential impacts on safety and suggesting future research directions.

IV.PROPOSED SYSTEM

In our proposed method, cameras track eye movements in real-time, capturing patterns for further analysis. These patterns are then processed by Convolutional Neural Networks, which are trained to recognize specific commands or actions by accurately interpreting various movement patterns. The interpreted movements are then converted into actionable commands to control the trolley, ensuring precise execution of user intentions. The system promptly responds to these commands, enabling smooth and responsive navigation, providing users with immediate feedback on their actions. Deep learning algorithms continuously learn and adapt to user behaviors and preferences, optimizing the system's performance over time. An intuitive interface simplifies interaction, offering visual feedback and customizable settings. Additionally, voice commands and item recognition enhance usability and accessibility, allowing users to engage with the system through alternative methods. Integration of RFID-equipped lift mechanisms seamlessly grants access to elevated areas within stores, enhancing overall accessibility for users with disabilities

V. BLOCK DIAGRAM

BLOCK DIAGRAM

PC UNIT:

WHEEL CHAIR UNIT:

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Software

VI. DESIGN AND SELECTION OF COMPONENTS

A. Arduino Uno

Arduino is the main part of the project; hence it should be selected properly. In our project we have selected Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P. It has 14 digital input/output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz quartz crystal, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with a AC-to-DC adapter. Arduino Uno has a number of facilities for communicating with a computer, another Arduino board, or other microcontrollers.

B. ZIGBEE (WSN)

ZigBee devices must adhere to the IEEE 802.15.4-2003 Low Rate Wireless Personal Area Network (LR-WPAN) standard, which specifies the physical layer (PHY) and the Media Access Control (MAC) portion of the data link layer (DLL). ZigBee technology, as outlined in the specification, aims to be simpler and more cost-effective compared to other wireless personal area networks (WPANs) like Bluetooth or Wi-Fi. With low power consumption, ZigBee devices have a transmission range of 10–100 meters in a line-of-sight scenario, influenced by power output and environmental factors. Utilizing a mesh network, ZigBee devices can transmit data over longer distances by relaying data through intermediate devices. ZigBee is commonly employed in applications requiring low data rates and extended battery life, ensuring secure networking. Its defined data rate of 250 kbit/s makes it particularly suitable for sporadic data transmissions from sensors or input devices.

C. RFID READER AND TAG

RFID tags serve as a tracking system utilizing radio frequency to locate, identify, monitor, and communicate with various items and individuals. These tags essentially function as intelligent labels capable of storing a diverse array of information, ranging from serial numbers to brief descriptions and even extensive data pages. Comprising an antenna and an integrated circuit (IC), RFID tags operate with the antenna transmitting and receiving RF signals, while the IC stores the tag's ID and other pertinent data.

The RFID reader, which can be either portable or permanently affixed, is a network-connected device. It emits radio waves to activate the tag, prompting it to send a response back to the antenna, where it is decoded into usable data. The transponder, embedded within the RFID tag itself, facilitates this communication process.

In contrast to a traditional barcode scanner, an RFID scanner employs electromagnetic waves for scanning. Utilizing an antenna, the scanner transmits signals to communicate with the tag's antenna. The tag then relays its unique chip information to the scanner. The data stored on the chip is typically in one of two memory types: Read-Only Memory (ROM), which cannot be altered once programmed during manufacturing, or Read/Write Memory (RAM), which allows for data modification.

RFID tags find application in various scenarios, such as being affixed to blood packs in blood banks for identification and tracking purposes using radio waves. In shopping malls, RFID tags are integrated into items for inventory management. Moreover, RFID systems are highly effective in safeguarding newborns in hospitals, where specially designed tags attached to both the baby and mother, along with tag readers and automated systems, aid in management and security efforts.

E.BATTERY

A battery is a device that directly converts chemical energy into electrical energy. It comprises multiple voltaic cells, with each cell composed of two half cells connected in series via a conductive electrolyte containing anions and cations. One half-cell consists of electrolyte and an electrode where anions migrate, known as the anode or negative electrode. The other half-cell includes electrolyte and an electrode where cations migrate, referred to as the cathode or positive electrode. In the redox reaction driving the battery, cations are reduced (gaining electrons) at the cathode, while anions are oxidized (losing electrons) at the anode. The electrodes are not physically connected but are electrically linked by the electrolyte. Some cells employ two half-cells with different electrolytes, with a separator between them allowing ion flow while preventing electrolyte mixing.

F.MOTOR DRIVER AND RELAYS

A relay driver circuit functions as a switching mechanism to control the operation of a relay, allowing it to appropriately switch the connected load. It is utilized to activate or deactivate the relay based on the requirements of the circuit and its operation. A relay, essentially an electromechanical switch, is responsible for altering the connection of an external load by switching its contacts in response to a relatively low electrical power applied across its coil.

The coil, typically wound around an iron core, acts as an electromagnet when a small DC voltage is applied. 5-pin relays consist of two pins for controlling the coil, while the remaining three pins include normally open, normally closed, and common connections. These relays facilitate the switching of high voltage using low voltage between two circuits, providing options for both normally open and normally closed connections. When the coil is energized, the power is redirected from the normally closed pin to the normally open pin.

In our project, the microcontroller operates at a minimum voltage of 5V DC, whereas the relay's working voltage is 12V DC. The microcontroller can be employed to drive larger loads, as it controls the load with a digital signal. The digital circuit output pulse biases the transistor to the ON state, subsequently activating the relay to switch the load between ON and OFF states.

G.DC MOTOR

Geared dc motors can be defined as an extension of dc motors. A geared DC Motor has a gear assembly attached to the motor. The speed of motor is counted in terms of rotations of the shaft per minute and is termed as RPM. The gear assembly helps in increasing the torque and reducing the speed. Using the correct combination of gears in a gear motor, its speed can be reduced to any desirable figure. This concept where gears reduce the speed of the vehicle but increase its torque is known as gear reduction.

VII. SOFTWARE INSTALLATION

Arduino IDE and embedded c program are used as software tools.

A.ARDUINO IDE

A program for Arduino hardware can be written in any programming language supported by compilers capable of producing binary machine code for the target processor. Atmel offers a development environment for their 8-bit AVR and 32-bit ARM Cortex-M based microcontrollers, such as AVR Studio (older) and Atmel Studio (newer). Overall, the Arduino IDE provides a comprehensive development environment for programming Arduino boards, enabling users to quickly prototype and develop projects for various applications. The IDE includes a code editor with features

such as syntax highlighting, automatic indentation, and code completion, making it easier to write and navigate code. Arduino IDE comes with a set of built-in libraries that provide functions for interfacing with various sensors, actuators, and other hardware components. These libraries simplify the process of programming by abstracting complex functionality into simple function calls. The IDE allows users to compile their code with just a click of a button. It also provides a simple interface for uploading compiled code to Arduino boards via USB or other communication interfaces.

The binary code of Arduino is illustrated in Figure A

Fig A. Binary code of Arduino

Integrated Development Environment (IDE)

The Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) is a cross-platform application compatible with Windows, macOS, and Linux. It is primarily written in the Java programming language and originated from the IDE for languages such as Processing and Wiring. The IDE features a comprehensive code editor equipped with various functionalities including text cutting and pasting, text search and replace, automatic indentation, brace matching, and syntax highlighting. Additionally, it offers convenient one-click mechanisms for compiling and uploading programs to an Arduino board.

Furthermore, the Arduino IDE comprises a message area, a text console, a toolbar with common function buttons, and a hierarchical menu structure. The source code for the IDE is released under the General Public License GNU.

The Arduino IDE supports programming languages C and C++, utilizing specific code structuring rules. It also provides a software library from the Wiring project, offering numerous common input and output procedures. User-written code typically necessitates only two fundamental functions: one for initializing the sketch and another for the main program loop. These functions are compiled and linked with a program stub `main()` into an executable cyclic executive program using the GNU toolchain, which is included in the IDE distribution.

Moreover, the Arduino IDE employs a program argument to convert the executable code into a text file encoded in hexadecimal format. This file is subsequently loaded into the Arduino board by a loader program embedded in the board's firmware.

B.Embedded C

Embedded C is an extension of the C programming language, developed by the C Standards committee, specifically tailored to address common challenges encountered in embedded systems development. These systems often require nonstandard extensions to C to support advanced microprocessor features such as fixed-point arithmetic, multiple memory banks, and basic I/O operations. The C Standards committee introduced enhancements to the language in 2008 to provide a unified standard for embedded systems development, including support for fixed-point arithmetic, named address spaces, and low-level hardware access.

Embedded C retains most of the syntax and semantics of standard C, including main() function, variable declarations, data types, conditional statements (if, switch case), loops (while, for), functions, arrays, strings, structures, unions, bit operations, macros, and more.

Embedded software refers to computer software designed to control non-computer devices, known as embedded systems. It is optimized for the specific hardware it runs on and is subject to constraints such as time and memory limitations. Embedded software is often referred to interchangeably with firmware.

A defining characteristic of embedded software is that it may not be directly initiated or controlled via a human interface, relying instead on machine interfaces. Manufacturers integrate embedded software into various devices, including cars, telephones, modems, robots, appliances, toys, security systems, pacemakers, televisions, set-top boxes, and digital watches. The complexity of embedded software can vary greatly, from simple lighting controls on a microcontroller with limited memory to sophisticated applications requiring advanced computation frameworks.

VIII.RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The implementation of the AI-based eyeball movement detection system in shopping trolleys has yielded significant positive outcomes, including improved accessibility and increased independence for individuals with disabilities. Through its real-time response and personalized adaptation capabilities, the system has enhanced efficiency and usability, garnering positive feedback from users. Moving forward, continued research and development efforts will focus on refining the system's capabilities and expanding its deployment to further promote inclusivity and accessibility in retail environments.

IX. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of AI-based eyeball movement detection technology in shopping trolleys represents a groundbreaking step towards promoting accessibility and independence for individuals with disabilities. By leveraging advanced computer vision algorithms and deep learning techniques, the system has successfully empowered users to navigate shopping environments autonomously, enhancing their overall quality of life. As we continue to innovate and refine this technology, we remain committed to fostering inclusivity and creating more accessible retail environments for all individuals, regardless of their abilities.

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